
TRADITIONS OF TEACHING GIRLS CRAFTS IN KARAKALPAK PEDAGOGY (FOLKLORE EXAMPLE)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7812592>

Doshmuratova Gulbaharim

Assistant, Karakalpak state university after named Berdakh

Abstract.

Handicraft is a folk-traditional small-scale production based on individual and manual labor using simple tools; the general name of the professions in which such products are produced. It was widespread until large-scale industrial production arose, and some industries survived after that. It still plays an important role in the economies of less developed countries. This article discusses the traditions of Karakalpak folk pedagogy in teaching crafts to girls.

Keywords.

crafts; civilization; folk arts and crafts; teaching tradition.

An integral part of human culture, folk art occupies a special place in the life of every people of the world, in the development of their way of life and values. The appearance of crafts in the conscious life of mankind is the most important historical step on the path to civilization. We among the people have a saying: "Craft - your earnings."

Indeed, the profession glorifies a person. This increases his respect among the people. Since the first years of our country's independence, much attention has been paid to the professional training of our youth. The huge opportunities created for private entrepreneurship give impetus to the development of family businesses in our country. As a result, young people can learn a profession by providing jobs.

Crafts have played an important role in the economy of the peoples of Central Asia since ancient times, especially in Karakalpakstan. In our century, the industry has retained some of its ancient traditions. Although the main occupation of the Karakalpaks is fishing and animal husbandry, handicrafts also form an important part of their life. It had a wide range of industries including blacksmithing, wood and metal working, embroidery, sewing, leather and jewelry. In Central Asia, including Karakalpakstan, the ethnographic features of handicraft traditions are also reflected in the production of handicrafts.

In the 19th and early 20th centuries, the production of jewelry was widespread in all trade and craft centers. Every large village had its own jeweler. Karakalpak jewelers used silver, gold, bronze, carnelian and turquoise stones, as well as necklaces, nails and hairpins of birds of prey for their products.

The Karakalpak jewelry style is distinguished by luxury, symmetrical shape and bright rounded contours. Jewelers mainly produced women's jewelry and children's amulets. For men, rings, belts and buckles, parts of weapons and horse equipment are made. All jewelry is considered a talisman that protects from evil and leads to happiness.

The Karakalpaks had national traditions, national costumes, jewelry, woodcarving, pottery, embroidery, carpet weaving. However, due to its geographical position in the Middle Ages, there were trade relations with other peoples.

The economy is on the rise. Karakalpaks sold or exchanged handicrafts to other countries. Men were engaged in blacksmithing, house building, carpentry and hunting, while women were mainly engaged in embroidery and weaving. The national costumes of the Karakalpak women are one of the most interesting elements of their material culture. Well-preserved women's clothing has been studied by scientists.

Thanks to the wide tradition of teaching crafts to girls in Karakalpak folk pedagogy, today embroidery and textile crafts are highly developed, national costumes, gifts are embroidered, designed and sold in Karakalpak shops. The reputation of the museum, known as the "Desert Louvre", is growing day by day. The work done to preserve the national heritage of the Karakalpak people, to present it to the general public, as well as to pass it on to future generations, is highly commendable.

As in all regions of the country, folk crafts have long been developed in the Aral Sea region. Especially in the family, teaching girls to embroider from an early age, bringing benefits to people with their products and labor, has become one of the primordial values of our people. In recent years, positive work has been done to support women artisans and ensure their employment. In our country, special attention is paid to the development of folk crafts, folk art crafts, employment of the unemployed, especially young people, women and low-income families. The construction of the lawn, which is another excellent kind of Karakalpak craft, and the mastery of the skills associated with its decoration, also require some work to restore. No tree can be used to regenerate grass. Its production is the original

heritage of the Karakalpak people. Interestingly, 70 percent of grass labor is created by women. That is, when the wood is restored, it is decorated with many types of patterns to give it the appearance of a whole ensemble, and they are made by hand. Therefore, in Karakalpakstan, special attention is paid to teaching boys and girls the secrets of this area of national needlework.

Among the crafts that glorify the nation, puppeteers are found in almost every region. In Karakalpak folk pedagogy, the creativity of women craftsmen, brought up on the traditions of teaching crafts to girls, is unique and colorful. They reflect the national culture and art of the Karakalpak people in paper and clay dolls and have won the admiration of countries around the world. It is known that the inhabitants of Karakalpakstan have always been engaged in textiles and needlework. At the same time, women gave this profession all their skills, abilities and craftsmanship. It was a kind of craft, forgotten due to the perfection of special machines, the choice of a certain place and season, in weaving various canvases from reeds. The Karakalpak people have recently left only a few masters of brass weaving.

This is due to the fact that a special machine called "kozak" and stones called "auruk" are hard to find and heavy, and it takes years to weave a single brass knuckles, as it is difficult to embroider. The practice of this type of craft showed a much lower level, leaving only a handful of our grandmothers. Since the Karakalpak girls have focused their attention on the development of national crafts, they have managed to revive endangered types of crafts by creating embroidery patterns, new types of patchwork quilts and a new style of zhezshi.

REFERENCES:

1. Archaeological and ethnographic works of the Khorezm expedition of 1945-1948 under the general editorship of Professor S. Tolstov and T.A. Zhdanko 1st volume Publishing House of the USSR Academy of Sciences Moscow -1952.
2. Isakov R. Traditions of Karakalpak folk crafts of the XX century. Tashkent. 2022.
3. 70% of weed is created by women. <https://uza.uz/uz/posts/tov-tiklashning-70-foiz-me-nati-ayellar-li-bilan-yaratiladi-19-06-2020>